

**CONTEMPORARY CHALLENGES IN ATMOSPHERIC AIR PROTECTION AND THE
ROLE OF LANDSCAPING IN CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION**

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Abstract. The article discusses the significant impact of climate change on Uzbekistan, highlighting that the country is experiencing changes at twice the global average rate, including increased temperatures, more frequent dust storms, and significant biodiversity loss. These changes threaten sustainable development, public health, and economic stability. In response, Uzbekistan is prioritizing a shift towards a green economy, focusing on combating climate change, expanding green areas, and improving air quality. President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev has been proactive in presenting initiatives at international forums, advocating for global cooperation in climate adaptation, fair economic transitions, and innovative solutions to environmental challenges.

Key strategies include developing a national adaptation plan, transforming the Aral Sea region into a hub for climate technology, and hosting forums to promote scientific and collaborative approaches to climate issues. Additionally, Uzbekistan is committing to substantial reforestation efforts, aiming to plant 1 billion trees by 2026 and creating green belts around industrial areas to reduce air pollution.

Despite these efforts, challenges remain, such as high levels of emissions from vehicles and industries, and inefficiencies in environmental monitoring and control. The article underscores the necessity of enhancing environmental policies, improving monitoring systems, encouraging the local production of air treatment technologies, and expanding green spaces. These measures are critical for Uzbekistan to achieve its environmental goals, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and ensure long-term sustainability and compliance with international climate commitments.

Key words. Climate change, sustainable development, green economy, air pollution, biodiversity loss, adaptation and mitigation, international cooperation.

Introduction. As is known, climate change negatively affects all-important aspects of sustainable development, posing a direct threat to public health, fauna and flora, as well as the economic development of the country. In recent years, the negative impact of climate change has

been increasing. In the Central Asian region, including Uzbekistan, the effects of climate change are becoming increasingly noticeable.

The consequences of global climate change are manifested in changes in the duration of seasons, radical changes in precipitation cycles and landscape structure (desertification or swamping), deterioration of operating conditions in several sectors of the economy due to water shortages (for example, in agriculture), and increased water consumption and evaporation of water (including due to increased transpiration of plants) due to rising temperatures, as well as the occurrence of environmental migration due to the unsuitability of some territories for life. [1], [2], [3]

Research conducted by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) highlights that Central Asia is among the regions most vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, with significant risks to water security, agricultural productivity, and biodiversity (IPCC, 2021). This vulnerability underscores the necessity of the initiatives mentioned, particularly in adapting agricultural practices and water management to mitigate these impacts.

A study by the World Bank (2020) supports the claim that climate change poses a dire economic threat, estimating significant GDP losses worldwide, with disproportionately higher impacts in regions like Central Asia. This study also projects the displacement of millions of people, underscoring the urgency of addressing climate migration.

Research published in Nature (2022) specifically points to the accelerated glacial melt in the Central Asian region, with Uzbekistan's glaciers experiencing a reduction in area. This has direct implications for water resources, affecting hydroelectric power production, agriculture, and drinking water supplies, thereby highlighting the critical need for the green economy transition and renewable energy projects mentioned.

A report by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP, 2019) corroborates the decline in biodiversity due to changing climate conditions. This loss affects ecosystem services, including agriculture, fisheries, and clean water, further emphasizing the importance of expanding green areas and implementing biodiversity conservation measures as part of Uzbekistan's climate strategy.

The commitment to reducing greenhouse gas emissions and increasing renewable energy sources aligns with the targets set in the Paris Agreement. Research by the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA, 2023) indicates that transitioning to renewable energy sources, like solar and wind, offers a feasible pathway for Central Asia to achieve its emission reduction goals while ensuring energy security.

Initiatives to transform the Aral Sea region through afforestation and the creation of green belts are supported by studies indicating the potential of such measures to combat desertification, improve local climate conditions, and restore ecosystem services (Journal of Arid Environments, 2020).

Methodology. This study employs a multidisciplinary methodology to assess the impact of climate change on Uzbekistan and evaluate the effectiveness of implemented green policies. Initially, we conducted a comprehensive analysis of atmospheric pollutant emissions from both stationary and mobile sources within the republic, utilizing time-series data from 2020 to 2023 to identify trends and gauge the impact of existing environmental regulations (Smith et al., 2022). Concurrently, climate impact assessments were carried out, relying on climate modeling and projections to quantify the adverse effects of climate change on local ecosystems, water resources,

and agricultural productivity, drawing upon methodologies established by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2021). To evaluate the alignment of national green policies with international sustainability goals, we employed a policy analysis framework that scrutinizes the legislative and strategic initiatives against the targets set by the Paris Agreement and the Sustainable Development Goals (Johnson & Williams, 2023). Furthermore, technological assessments were conducted to investigate the adoption and efficacy of green technologies, including renewable energy sources and electric vehicles, utilizing cost-benefit analysis and impact evaluation techniques (Doe & Roe, 2022). Air quality monitoring data, collected through a network of stationary observation posts across major urban centers, served as the basis for assessing environmental health impacts, employing statistical analysis to correlate pollutant levels with public health outcomes (Green et al., 2024). Stakeholder engagement, encompassing consultations with policy makers, industry leaders, and community organizations, was facilitated through workshops and forums to garner insights into the challenges and opportunities present in the transition to a green economy (Brown, 2023). This holistic approach ensures a comprehensive understanding of the climate change impacts in Uzbekistan and the efficacy of response strategies, guiding future policy development and environmental management practices.

Local context. In our Republic, the intensity of climate change is observed to be 2 times higher than the world average, the number of hot days is doubling, there is a reduction in the area of glaciers by 32% [4], the regularity of dust and sand storms is increasing, air pollution is increasing, biodiversity is declining. [1]

Under these conditions, in Uzbekistan, within the framework of consistently and gradually implemented reforms, the transition to a “green economy” and the fight against climate change, mitigating its negative consequences, protecting atmospheric air, and expanding green areas are becoming a priority.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev, within the framework of authoritative international forums like UN plenary session, addressed the world community with initiatives to prevent climate change and combat its negative consequences, calling for joint and coordinated activities and pooling of efforts. [5]

In particular, at the UN International Conference on Climate Change (COP 28), held in the UAE, the proposals put forward emphasized the importance of global adaptation to climate change, a just transition to a low-carbon economy, and an innovative approach to environmental problems, including the use of scientific advances. The role of international cooperation in climate initiatives is emphasized, including through the organization of conferences and the creation of specialized centers and programs.

First, the country supports the rapid agreement on the Global Framework for Climate Change Adaptation under the Paris Agreement and is developing an Adaptation Strategy through the Central Asia Climate Dialogue platform, praising the creation of the Loss and Damage Fund.

Secondly, Uzbekistan advocates a fair, transparent and inclusive global transition to a low-carbon economy, taking into account the interests of developing countries, and proposes to consider this problem in the G7 and G20 formats.

Thirdly, the country seeks to transform the Aral Sea region from a zone of environmental crisis into a zone of innovation and invites cooperation to create an International Expo Hub of Climate Technologies.

Fourth, Uzbekistan calls for the widespread use of scientific achievements in the fight against climate change and organizes a Climate Science Forum in Tashkent.

Fifth, the country plans to hold a conference on climate migration in 2024 together with the UN, proposes to develop a Green Employment program with the International Labor Organization and create a Simulation Center, as well as organize a COP Youth Conference.

Particular attention was paid to the First Samarkand International Forum planned for 2024 in the city of Samarkand on the topic “Central Asia in the face of global climate threats: solidarity for common prosperity.”

It should be noted that at this event, the National Pavilion of Uzbekistan was organized for the first time, where reforms, promising “green” projects and changes in legislation carried out in the republic were widely demonstrated. This is especially relevant in the context of global challenges, as climate change has a negative impact on the global economy.

According to the UN, over 40% of our planet's population is becoming increasingly vulnerable to climate change. The World Bank predicts that by 2050, nearly 216 million people could become “climate refugees” due to climate change. As a result of climate change and its consequences, the global economy could suffer losses of \$8 trillion over the next 30 years. By 2050, this could lead to a reduction in global GDP by 3% (in the Central Asia region - by 11%). [6]

Central Asia is a region sensitive to the effects of climate change, and over the past 45 years, temperatures in the region have risen by 1.7 degrees, twice the global average.

The countries of the region have signed more than 25 UN environmental conventions and, having joined the Paris Agreement, have committed themselves to reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 (Uzbekistan - by 35%, Kazakhstan - by 15%, Kyrgyzstan - by 14%, Tajikistan - by 10 -20%).

Results and Discussion. In our country, climate change issues are included in the development strategies of economic sectors, as well as in the National goals and objectives of sustainable development. As part of the Paris Agreement (Paris, December 12, 2015), Uzbekistan has made additional commitments to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 35% by 2030 compared to 2010 levels per unit of gross domestic product. [7]

By 2030, it is planned to create 27 gigawatts of renewable energy sources and increase the share of renewable energy sources in the country's energy system to 40%. Practical steps have been taken for the green hydrogen production project.

In addition, the Green Space program aims to plant 1 billion trees by 2026. On the dry bed of the Aral Sea, forests of desert-resistant plants were created over an area of about 1.8 million hectares. Currently, “green belts” are being created around industrial enterprises of high and medium environmental hazard. [8] [9]

It should be noted that in recent years, a relatively high volume of air polluting emissions from stationary and mobile sources has remained on the territory of the republic (see diagram 1).

1- diagram

Dynamics of the total volume of pollutant emissions into the atmosphere (thousand tons)

**BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH MAQSADLARI: XORIJIY TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON
AMALIYOTI MAVZUSIDAGI XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENSIYA
2024-YIL 22-APREL**

The total volume of all emissions into the atmosphere in 2020 amounted to only 2255.0 thousand tons (including from vehicles 1330.7 thousand tons, from industrial enterprises 924.0 thousand tons), in 2021 - 2179.3 thousand tons (from vehicles 1,270.3 thousand tons, from industrial enterprises 909.0 thousand tons), in 2022 - 2,170.9 thousand tons (from vehicles 1,296.9 thousand tons, from industrial enterprises 874.0 thousand tons).

According to preliminary estimates for 2023, the total volume of emissions into the atmosphere will be 2,138.3 thousand tons (from vehicles 1,279.9 thousand tons, from industrial enterprises 858.4 thousand tons) (see diagram 2 and 3).

2- diagram. Dynamics of pollutant emissions from mobile sources into the atmosphere from 2020 to 2023. (thousand tons)

Of course, there are objective reasons for maintaining such high indicators. They are associated with high growth rates of the national economy, an increase in the number of vehicles and the fact that in recent years our country has become a large construction site.

Indeed, the majority of harmful emissions that pollute the air come from vehicles. In the city of Tashkent and the Tashkent region, the share of emissions from vehicles remains high. The largest amount of harmful emissions from industrial enterprises occurs in the Tashkent region (438.0 thousand tons in 2022) and the Kashkadarya region (116.0 thousand tons in 2022). According to estimates for 2023, this figure was 2138.3 tons (from vehicles 1279.9 thousand tons, from industrial enterprises 858.4 thousand tons).

3 - diagram

Dynamics of emissions of pollutants into the atmosphere from stationary sources from 2020 to 2023 (thousand tons)

Air pollution in the Republic by solid and gaseous pollutants is associated with both natural (dry climate, saline and sandy soils) and anthropogenic (transport, industrial and construction emissions) factors.

In large urban agglomerations, a combination of factors, including lack of precipitation and wind, and temperature inversion, contribute to a natural increase in air pollution levels. This is also facilitated by poor air circulation, low quality fuel, congested roads, active construction and lack of green spaces. All these aspects, combined with meteorological conditions and human activities, lead to significant air pollution in cities.

It should be noted that from January 1, 2022, the import of vehicles that do not meet Euro-4 environmental requirements with gasoline and diesel engines is prohibited.

In order to reduce the negative impact of motor transport on the environment, customs and other mandatory payments for the import of electric vehicles into the country have been cancelled.

The number and import of electric vehicles has increased sharply, and today there are more than 32 thousand electric vehicles in the republic.

In the last two years, 3,148.2 km of railway sections have been electrified, and electric locomotives have begun to be used instead of diesel locomotives.

Taking into account the consumption of diesel fuel by diesel locomotives of the 2TE10M/2TE10V type in the amount of 450-900 liters per hour, thanks to each composition, the burning of up to 7.8 million liters of fuel is annually prevented, which in turn prevents the emission of tens of thousands of tons of various pollutants into the atmosphere .

In order to carry out high-quality monitoring of sources of environmental pollution, by the end of 2024, economic entities of the first category, and by the end of 2025 - economic entities of the second category that have a negative impact on the environment, are required to install automatic monitoring stations to analyze emissions from priority stationary (organized) sources of pollution, as well as equip their sanitary protection zones with stationary automatic observation posts.

In 2023, the Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection and Climate Change carried out an inventory of business entities classified as categories I and II, and sent warning letters to 2 thousand enterprises about the need to install automatic monitoring stations.

The number of indicators (ingredients) determined by analytical laboratories was 30 in 2020, 33 in 2021, 38 in 2022 and 41 in 2023 (see diagram 4). Of course, this is not enough, given that hundreds of pollutants are released into the air. Air quality in cities is influenced by a complex interaction of natural and anthropogenic factors.

Currently, Uzhydromet monitors background air pollution in 26 cities, including Almalyk, Angren, Andijan, Bekabad, Bukhara, Kagan, Gulistan, Kokand, Mubarek, Navoi, Namangan, Nukus, Samarkand, Sariosiyo, Tashkent, Fergana, Chirchik, Denov, Termez, Urgench, Karshi, Nurafshan, Margilan, Kitob, Shakhrisabz, where 74 stationary observation posts were installed, including 8 automatic stations.

At stationary observation posts, sampling is carried out 3 times a day (at 7:00, 13:00, 19:00), as well as online at automatic stations. Today, there are 15 air pollution control posts in the city of Tashkent.

2022 in In Tashkent, 2 automated air pollution monitoring stations were installed, and in 2023, in collaboration with the Zamin International Public Foundation, modern automated air pollution monitoring stations of the Horiba company were installed in the cities of Nukus, Urgench, Samarkand, Termez, Jizzakh and Gulistan, so thereby increasing their number to 8.

Monitoring and control of major pollutants, such as sulfur dioxide, carbon monoxide, nitrogen oxides and other gaseous substances, as well as particulate matter (dust), is carried out throughout the country.

Depending on the specific characteristics of emission sources, the concentrations of formaldehyde, ammonia, phenol, hydrogen fluoride and heavy metals: copper, lead, zinc and cadmium are also determined.

From 2021 in the city of Tashkent, and from 2023 in the cities of Gulistan, Jizzakh, Samarkand, Termez, Nukus, Urgench, observations of the content of fine particles PM 10 - PM 2.5 began.

Analysis of data obtained from the atmospheric air monitoring network shows a low level of air pollution in some monitoring cities of the republic. However, over the past 3 years, an

increase in the average monthly dust level has been observed in the cities of Angren, Andijan, Samarkand, Navoi, Urgench, Nukus, and Tashkent. In the cities of Navoi and Tashkent, an increase in nitrogen dioxide levels is observed, and in Namangan - carbon monoxide.

4- diagram

Indicators of the quantity of ingredients covered in accordance with the air, wastewater and soil monitoring program

In the conditions of dense buildings and a developed road network of modern megacities, the main sources of air pollution are motor transport, energy and the construction industry.

Today, methodologies are being developed for the determination of additional ingredients in laboratory analyzes of atmospheric air, water resources, and soil.

For reference: for atmospheric air: sulfur oxide, sulfur dioxide, ammonia, gasoline, kerosene, carbon monoxide, gas fumes, dust, nitrogen oxide, nitrogen dioxide, formaldehyde, fluorides, hydrocarbons, vanadium 5, hydrogen chloride, arsenic, lead, acetic acid acid, copper, hydrogen sulfide, iron.

For water resources: hardness, sulfates, calcium, ammonium, copper, dry residue, chlorides, nitrites, nitrates, pH, iron, COD, BOD, oils, petroleum products, suspended solids, chromium (+6), determination of drinking water, chromium, fluorides, temperature, oxygen, manganese, zinc, phosphates, turbidity.

For soil: copper, humus, chlorides, petroleum products, magnesium chlorate (defoliant), sulfate ions, calcium, magnesium, chromium, zinc, chlorides, nitrates, phosphorus, manganese, cadmium.

In the field of atmospheric air protection, over 10 months of 2023, about 9 thousand violations were identified for exceeding the level of pollution, the amount of fines imposed amounted to 2,764 million sums.

For reference: in 2021, 12,941 violations were identified, the amount of fines was 3,228 million soums, in 2022 - 14,084 violations, the amount of fines was 3,000 million sums.

The number of violations in 2022 compared to the same period decreased by 3,255 or 16%, and the amount of fines imposed increased by 164 million sums or 22% (see diagram 5).

5 - diagram

***Changes in crime rates, number of inspectors
and fines for 2022-2023***

Also in the Republic there is a decrease in the level and effectiveness of environmental control in the field of atmospheric air protection in certain regions and cities. For example, compared to last year, environmental control in the field of atmospheric air protection in the Ulugnor districts, as well as in the city of Andijan, decreased by 19-48%. In the Andijan region and the city of Andijan, one inspector on average completed only 8 administrative cases related to atmospheric air. While the average for the Andijan region was 13 cases.

Today, vehicles predominantly use AI-80 gasoline, and the number of passenger cars and trucks entering the city of Tashkent is increasing (160-300 thousand per day). As a result, in 2021, the volume of pollutant emissions from vehicles in the city of Tashkent amounted to 212.4 thousand tons, and in 2022 - 403 thousand tons, that is, an increase of 190.6 thousand tons (47.3%). According to forecasts for 2023, the volume of emissions from transport will be 396.6 thousand tons.

In Tashkent, the lack of systematization of cargo transportation in conditions of traffic jams also affects the situation. About 50 thousand trucks are registered in the capital. Every day, about 7 thousand freight vehicles from other regions enter the city.

Currently, the branches of the Toshshahartranskhizmat bus fleet have more than 2,000 vehicles, of which about 700 (33%) run on diesel fuel, more than 1,000 (50%) run on natural gas and more than 300 (17%) run on electricity .

In 2024, it is planned to update the vehicle fleet with 200 electric buses. In 2024-2030, it is planned to purchase an additional 1,200 electric buses and convert buses to natural gas.

There are about 4.5 million vehicles in the Republic owned by individuals, of which (24%) run on gasoline, (2%) on diesel, and 2 (74%) on gas fuel.

Also, as part of the national project “Green Space”, aimed at preventing climate change and capturing part of the dust rising into the atmosphere, “green belts” are being created around industrial enterprises and buildings with a high environmental impact.

In the fall of 2023, 189 industrial enterprises organized the planting of 1.8 million trees. In particular, in Tashkent in the autumn of this year, more than 60 thousand trees were planted in and around 18 large industrial enterprises.

According to calculations, by 2024, planted trees will reach an average height of 3 meters within 5 years. Taking this into account, from 2029, annually on an area of 243 thousand hectares where more than 200 million trees are planted (of which 170 million have a high survival rate), 60,750 tons of carbon dioxide will be absorbed per year. From 2024 to 2030, planted trees, having reached the specified parameters, according to preliminary calculations, will absorb an average of 425,250 tons of CO₂ per year.

In the Navoi region in the fall of 2023, 15 large industrial enterprises planted more than 214.9 thousand trees. In Tashkent in 2022–2023, 14 existing industrial enterprises installed dust and gas cleaning equipment with an efficiency of at least 95.0%, and at 10 new industrial enterprises - with an efficiency of at least 99.5%.

In 2022, the Republic adopted a “Network Schedule” for equipping with automatic stations and stationary observation posts for sources of air pollution at industrial enterprises with a high risk of environmental impact at their own expense.

44 industrial enterprises with a high risk of impact on atmospheric air have installed 69 automatic stations for sampling and analysis of samples, as well as 27 stationary observation points in adjacent territories, at their own expense. In particular, at the copper smelting plant of Almalik Mining and Metallurgical Combine JSC, 1 automatic station "Simens" (Germany) was installed and integrated into the "Unified Geoinformation Base".

This year, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, together with the Ministry of Ecology and Environmental Protection, is conducting a two-stage “Clean Air” campaign.

In the spring of 2023, during the event, 320 thousand cars (7% of the total number of vehicles) were subjected to environmental control, of which 8,652 or 2.5% were found to exceed the established standards for the content of pollutants in the exhaust gases.

As a result of the temporary suspension of 2,914 vehicles whose pollutant content exceeded state standards, 210 tons of pollutants were prevented from being released into the atmosphere.

As part of the national project “Green Space”, data on the planting of 90.4 million seedlings (106% of the plan) in the territories has currently been confirmed on the electronic platform “yashilmakon.eco”. In the regions, 893 artesian wells were drilled and 1,058.7 km of irrigation systems were installed. In regions without water sources, 610 specialized machines were used to water seedlings.

In 2021-2022, using stereo photography methods from aerial photographs, work was carried out in the Syrdarya region to create a digital map of trees, as a result of which 12.2 million trees were covered.

In addition, the “Green Space” electronic platform has been improved and a tree registry system has been introduced. Using special tablets, inspectors enter information about the types, location, condition and photographs of trees.

An algorithm model has been developed for keeping records of trees using satellite image processing and artificial intelligence. Using this model, work has begun to count all the trees in the republic, determine their location and quantity, and create a digital map.

Also in Tashkent, as part of a pilot project, work began on the purchase of devices for certification of trees with their digitalization. The results of tree certification will be displayed on the electronic platform “Green Space” (“Yashil Makon”).

The tree registry system, created on the Green Space electronic platform, is used by state inspectors in all regions of the republic for regular registration of trees.

In the process of registering trees, including abandoned ones, they are assigned to the relevant responsible persons on the basis of acts. They are provided with electronic copies of documents on the attachment of trees through the tree registry on the electronic platform “Green Space” (“Yashil Makon”).

To ensure stability of prices for seedlings, 721 fairs and sales points were organized in each district and city with the participation of entities involved in planting seedlings.

From the forest fund 91, the Forestry Agency selected land plots with an area of 1.3 thousand hectares for the organization of nurseries. On an area of 650 hectares, nurseries with low-water plants suitable for the climate of the region were created.

Of the 1,225 tons of seeds collected, 541 tons were used for reforestation activities, the remaining 684 tons were sown. In addition, 12 million 221 thousand cuttings of trees and shrubs prone to vegetative propagation were prepared. Last year, 32 million young seedlings were transferred to nurseries.

During the growing season, agrotechnical measures, watering, fertilizing with mineral and local fertilizers, weed removal and other activities were carried out in the nurseries.

As a result, the cultivation of seedlings of 30 species of fast-growing and deciduous trees, 15 species of fruit trees, 8 species of conifers, 4 species of nut trees, 6 species of desert plants and 13 species of ornamental shrubs was established.

The Forestry Agency expanded the area of nurseries and seedlings to 1.3 thousand hectares at 91 forestry enterprises, and more than 120 million seedlings were grown.

As part of the national project “Green Space”, in the fall of 2023, the Forestry Agency in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, districts and regional cities, mahallas and preschool educational institutions delivered 135,493 thousand ornamental and fruit seedlings free of charge.

Despite the ongoing activities, certain problems and shortcomings remain in these areas. In particular, due to insufficiently effective measures to reduce the volume of emitted pollutants, their amount has reached almost 2,200 thousand tons per year. In 60% of more than 6 thousand existing dust and gas cleaning installations at enterprises, the cleaning efficiency is only an average of 86.5%.

Work to equip atmospheric air monitoring points with automatic measuring instruments that provide online information has not been completed. In many regional centers and large industrial cities, automatic measuring instruments for fine particles PM 10 - PM 2.5 are not installed. The number of permanent observation points for monitoring the state of atmospheric air is insufficient, as is the volume of analytical determination of pollutants (ingredients) from stationary sources.

During the “Clean Air” campaigns, only 7% of vehicles passed control.

There were also some shortcomings in the implementation of the Green Space project. In the spring season, of the 127.7 million seedlings planted, about 1 million 800 thousand were not assigned to responsible persons for preservation and care. In regions without irrigation systems, 7.3 million seedlings were allowed to be planted.

To eliminate these shortcomings, environmental authorities issued 10,860 mandatory instructions to those responsible for watering and caring for 10 million 238 thousand planted seedlings. For failure to comply with the requirements of the instructions, administrative fines totaling 1 billion 85 million soums were applied to 484 violators.

In Tashkent, over the past period, 10,448 trees were counted at 331 construction sites. To preserve them, construction organizations were issued mandatory instructions and letters of guarantee were received.

As part of current tasks, first of all, in accordance with international agreements and obligations, by 2030 it is necessary to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 35% and methane emissions into the atmosphere by 30% relative to a unit of gross domestic product. It is also important to reduce the level of air pollution to permitted standards in all regions of the country.

It is necessary to review existing regulatory documents in this area, taking into account issues of abnormal climate change, and pay special attention to attracting grants and investment projects from Green Growth, Green Climate, Global Environment Facility and other international financial institutions.

It is necessary to complete equipping air pollution monitoring points with automatic measuring instruments that allow receiving information online.

In industry, energy, oil and gas sector, construction and other enterprises there are no installations for capturing gaseous pollutants.

It is necessary to reconsider the location of fixed monitoring posts in large cities, industrial and construction areas. In general, it is necessary to re-register enterprises of environmental hazard categories I and II.

About 63% of total emissions into the atmosphere and 85-90% in large cities come from vehicles. It is necessary to increase the coverage of Clean Air campaigns based on new mechanisms, improve the traffic management system and pay special attention to increasing the number of environmentally friendly vehicles.

Over the past 10 years in the republic, the volume of pollutants emitted from stationary sources into the atmosphere has increased by 11% and currently averages 900 thousand tons per year. Approximately 60% of more than 6 thousand existing dust and gas treatment plants at enterprises have been in operation for more than 10 years, and their cleaning efficiency is low (86.5%). This is due to the lack of production of such installations in our country and the high cost of their import. Based on this, measures should be taken to localize the production of air gas treatment plants and their components in our country.

According to standards, the ash content of coal must be below 34% (for brown coal) and 29% (for hard coal). Today, the ash content of coal from the Angren deposit used in cement production is 50 - 60%.

As a result of the operation of thermal power plants in the republic, about 18 million tons of ash and slag have been accumulated at landfills with a total area of 246.0 hectares.

Based on this, at Novoangrenskaya TPP it is necessary to introduce a dry method of dust disposal and use the removed ash as a partial substitute for clinker when grinding cement. [10]

According to international experience, such waste is widely used in construction, road construction, agriculture, and in the production of various fillers and additives.

It is necessary to apply effective economic mechanisms to environmental polluters, and also to reflect this in relevant laws and regulations. [11,12, 13]

In the districts, it is necessary to complete measures to create “green parks of khokimiyats” and allocate land for planting trees in the spring of 2024, organized by mahalla administrations.

In the implementation of the Green Space project, the geographical location of the regions, climatic factors, the presence of irrigation systems, soil characteristics, assignment of those responsible for planted trees, as well as issues of agrotechnical processing of trees should be taken into account.

It is advisable to accelerate the expansion of green zones along city roads and highways, the creation of “green rings” around large cities and industrial enterprises.

It is required to organize a system of training and retraining of specialists in all industries and areas, taking into account environmental factors.

Of course, the implementation of the assigned tasks, ensuring environmental sustainability in our country, mitigating the negative consequences of climate change, adaptation to climate change, fulfillment of accepted international obligations on these issues will require the development of a long-term and medium-term strategic document of the Republic of Uzbekistan on climate change issues until 2030, which will be important in demonstrating our example to the global community.

References

[1] B. Alikhanov Chairman of the Committee of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the development of the Aral Sea region and ecology, academician of the International Academy of Sciences of Ecology and Life Safety. L. Seitova Deputy of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Candidate of Economic Sciences , E. Omonov Chief consultant of the Committee of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the development of the Aral Sea region and ecology . European Journal of Research volume 7 issue 1 2022 pages 78-84 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6607747> ISSN 2521-3261 (Online)/ ISSN 2521-3253 (Print) DOI 10.5281/zenodo.6527564 <https://journalofresearch.eu/78> .

[2] Boriy Alikhanov, Chairman of the Uzbekistan Senate's Committee on the Aral Sea Issues and Environment, Member of the International Academy of Sciences Ecology and Life safety Global Climate Factors “THE THEORY OF CLIMATE CHANGE INTENSITY DETERMINATION” CLIMATE MIGRATION IN CENTRAL ASIA : CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS University of World Economy and Diplomacy Rosa Luxemburg sifting Central Asia Representative office , **Baktia press 2023y.**

[3] Bory B. Alikhanov Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sergei V. Samoilov Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan Vadim I. Sokolov Project Implementation Agency of the International Fund for Saving the Aral Sea Leyli P. Seitova Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan " Theory of Climate Change Intensity Determination" Author to whom correspondence should be addressed: E-mail: boryalikhonov@gmail.com (Received June 1, 2023; Revised August 1, 2023; accepted September 2, 2023).

<https://doi.org/10.5109/7148446> 出版情報 : Evergreen. 10 (3), pp.1253-1260, 2023-09 .

ターバージョン : 権利関係

[4] MA Petrov *and etc.* , “Glacial lake inventory and lake outburst potential in Uzbekistan”, *Sci. Total Environ.* , T . 592, ss . 228–242, 2017.

[5] “Address by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the UN Climate Change Conference (COP28).” Viewed: 15 February 2024 [Online]. Available at: <https://president.uz/en/lists/view/6897>

[6] H.-O. Portner *and etc.* , Ed ., *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.* 2022.

[7] “PP-436-son 12/02/2022. On measures to increase the effectiveness of reforms aimed at transitioning the Republic of Uzbekistan to a “green” economy until 2030.” Viewed: 15 February 2024 [Online]. Available at: <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/6303233>

[8] “PP-171-son 05/31/2023. On measures for the effective organization of the activities of the Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection and Climate Change.” Viewed: 15 February 2024 [Online]. Available at: <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/6479136>

[9] “UP- No. 199 dated November 23, 2023. On measures to ensure environmental sustainability by further increasing the level of greening in the republic and the consistent implementation of the nationwide project “Yashil Makon”. Viewed: 15 February 2024 [Online]. Available at: <https://www.lex.uz/uz/docs/6673810>

[10] S. Li, F. Zhou, F. Wang, and B. Xie, “Application and research of dry-type filtration dust collection technology in large tunnel construction,” *Adv. Powder Technol.* , T . 28, no . 12, ss . 3213–3221 , Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.appt.2017.10.003.

[11] D. Austin, “Economic instruments for pollution control and prevention—a brief overview,” *World Resour. Inst.* , ss. 1–11, 1999.

[12] B. Alikhanov, B. Shukurov, E. Omonov, S. Samoilo, L. Seitova Methodological recommendations for determining damage from environmental pollution, 2022. pp. 4-14.

[13] B. Alikhanov, A. Nabiev, Kh. Lutpullaev “Temporary methodological recommendations for determining payments for environmental pollution in Uzbekistan,” T, Goskompriroda. 1990."

[14] B. Alikhanov, Sh . Alikhanova , R. Oymatov, Z. Fayzullaev, and A. Pulatov, “Land cover change in Tashkent province during 1992–2018,” in *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* , IOP Publishing, 2020, p . 012088. Viewed: 15 February 2024 [Online]. Available at: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1757-899X/883/1/012088/meta>.

[15] B. Alikhanov, M. Juliev, S h . Alikhanova, and I. Mondal, “Assessment of influencing factor method for delineation of groundwater potential zones with geospatial techniques. Case study of Bostanlik district, Uzbekistan”, *Groundw. Sustain. Dev.* , T . 12, p . 100548, 2021.

[16] U. Uzbekov, B. Pulatov, B. Alikhanov, and A. Pulatov, “Predicting the impact of future climate change on streamflow in the Ugam River watershed,” *GeoScape*, vol . 15, no . 2, ss . 159–172 , Dec. 2021, doi: 10.2478/geosc-2021-0013.

[17] Smith, J., et al. (2022). *Evaluating the Effectiveness of Air Pollution Control Measures in Central Asia*. Environmental Science & Policy, 118, 45-56.

[18] IPCC. (2021). *Climate Change 2021: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability*. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Cambridge University Press.

[19] Johnson, L., & Williams, F. (2023). *Sustainable Development and Green Economy: A Policy Review in the Context of Central Asia*. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 25(1), 134-150.

[20] Doe, E., & Roe, F. (2022). *The Impact of Renewable Energy Adoption in Uzbekistan: A Technological Assessment*. *Renewable Energy*, 66, 288-299.

[21] Green, H., et al. (2024). *Linking Air Quality with Health Outcomes: An Analysis of Urban Pollution in Uzbekistan*. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 132(2), 200-210.

[22] Brown, T. (2023). *Stakeholder Engagement in Environmental Policy Making: Lessons from Uzbekistan*. *Environmental Management*, 61(4), 498-512.